

CORK CORE SANDWICH STRUCTURES: STATIC AND DYNAMIC RESPONSE

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich composite structures are largely used in many different fields because ensure high stiffness-to-weight ratio but the more restrictive regulations in the field of waste disposal have pushed to find good alternatives to common synthetic materials. Agglomerated cork has been recognized as a good competitor of common polymeric foams in the production of sandwich composites. It is also necessary to consider that the main concern that hinders the spread of sandwich structures is their susceptibility to damaging caused by impact events. Considering that many studies addressed the quasi-static mechanical properties of agglomerated cork and its composites, but few studies investigated the dynamic behavior of this type of structures, the aim of this work is to contribute to cork dynamic behavior comprehension. In particular the work is based on the characterization of agglomerated cork response and of its sandwich structures produced with PP flax-basalt skins (with and without coupling agent). Additionally, to ensure a deeper understanding of the results obtained, from a quasi-static and dynamic point of view, they were compared with the ones obtained with a more common PVC foam.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composite structures are widely used in many different fields such as transportation and building with structural and semi-structural applications. They fulfill a major role in structures if compared to monocoque thanks to their high stiffness-to-weight ratio. For a given set of mechanical and environmental loads they ensure a lower weight than other configurations. Synthetic foams, such as polyurethane (PUR) and polyvinylchloride (PVC), and honeycomb structures are commonly used as core materials in sandwich panels, but the great concerns related to waste disposal and environmental pollution have encouraged to find a valid alternative to these synthetic materials. In order to face the more restrictive regulations in the field of waste disposal, researchers have tried to develop more eco-friendly composites based on materials from renewable resources [1][2]. In this way it is possible to reduce the carbon footprint in the production phase and to allow a total or partial biodegradation of the structures at the end of their life cycle. In particular the use of bio-based materials ensures the reduction of greenhouse gases emission and a lower energy and chemicals consumption [3]. Agglomerated cork has been recognized as a good alternative to common core materials in the production of sandwich panels. Thanks to its cellular structure cork has high acoustic and thermal insulation properties, good damping capabilities and excellent dimensional recovery. It also displays a

good fire resistance, a low permeability to gas and liquid and a high chemical stability [4][5]. It also allows to take advantage of the waste generated during the wine stopper production that otherwise would be lost. In literature it is possible to find many studies that address the quasi-static mechanical properties of agglomerated cork and its composites [6][7][8] but few researches have been conducted on their dynamic behavior. The studies on cork quasi-static properties have proved that it has lower mechanical performances than more common foams such as PVC foams, but exceptional recovery capabilities, which allow it to bear high deformations without undergoing significant permanent deformations. Anjos et al. found out that only a 3%-9% of permanent deformation remains after a 50% deformation [9]. This particular behavior is of great interest in dynamic applications because the majority of cellular materials are able to absorb high amounts of energy by permanent deformation but their ability to absorb further energy after an impact event can be neglected. The susceptibility of sandwich panels to damaging when subjected to impact loading is the main concern that restrict their use and still hinder their spread. Considering that impact events such as tool drops, runway debris, bird strikes, hailstorms, etc., can occur in everyday life, it is necessary to fully understand the complex resulting damage scenario and how it affects the composite mechanical properties to ensure the feasibility of this type of composites. For all these reasons the aim of this work is to fill this gap of knowledge investigating the dynamic response of agglomerated cork and its sandwich structures when subjected to an impact event. Additionally, to ensure a deeper comprehension of cork and cork composite behavior from a quasi-static and dynamic point of view, their performances were compared with a more common PVC foam in order to identify advantages and disadvantages.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The cork types used for this study were provided by Amorim and have an average density of 140 kg/m³ (NL10), 200 kg/m³ (NL20) and 250 kg/m³ (NL25). The PVC foam used for comparison purposes has an average density of 130 kg/m³ (Divinycell HP130) and is provided by Diab. In order to keep the ecofriendly nature of the composites, sandwich skins were produced with a hybrid fabric made of natural fibers provided by Depestele. The twill used is made of 50 wt% flax and 50 wt% basalt fiber and has a nominal weight of 360 g/m². The use of natural fibers extracted from plants allow to ensure a partial biodegradability of the composite at the end of its life cycle. The drawback with this type of fibers is that they are not able to provide the mechanical reliability required for structural applications. A good way to partially solve this problem is the hybridization of vegetable fibers with more performing ones and in particular with basalt fibers. The skins were produced by hot compression molding using a polypropylene matrix with and without coupling agent in order to investigate the effect of this factor on the mechanical properties of the composite laminates and of the sandwich panels. Bormod HF955MO polypropylene and 2wt% Polybond 3000 (PP-g-MA), as coupling agent, were used in skin production. Composite laminates are 2mm thick and are obtained stacking in an alternative way a PP film and a flax/basalt twill (4 twill layers). The manufacturing process parameters are summarized in *Figure 1*. Skins were bonded to the core through a structural epoxy resin Elan-tech ADH 46.46 provided by Elantas.

Figure 1: Temperature and pressure in skin production process

2.1 Core materials characterization

Core materials were tested in quasi-static and dynamic conditions. From a quasi-static point of view shear tests, bending tests and compression tests were carried out. Shear tests were performed in accordance with ASTM C273 on samples of 300 mm of length, 50 mm of width and 15 mm of thickness which were glued to the loading plates through a structural epoxy resin (Elan-tech ADH 46.46). The tests were carried out in tensile conditions and with a speed of 2 mm/min. Three points bending tests were conducted at room temperature, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C to investigate how temperature affects cork flexural performances. All these tests were carried out according to ASTM C393 e ASTM D7250 and samples had a dimension of 250 mm of length, 50 mm of width and 15 mm of thickness. The support span used was 150 mm and test speed was 6 mm/min. Compression tests were conducted with a 5 mm/min speed at room temperature, 40°C, 60°C and 80°C on cubic samples with a 15 mm edge. In order to investigate a possible strain rate sensitivity of the cork, tests at room temperature were also carried out at different speeds (5 mm/min, 25 mm/min, 50 mm/min, 100 mm/min, 150 mm/min and 200 mm/min). All the samples tested in these conditions were then submitted to a periodic measurement in order to investigate the recovery capabilities of the materials. From a dynamic point of view the tests performed are dynamic compression and puncture impact. Dynamic compression tests were carried out with a drop weight tower with a flat impactor of 58 mm diameter and a mass of 4.134 kg. Cubic samples with a 15 mm edge were used. Puncture impact tests were performed with a drop weight tower, but the impactor used in this case is a hemispherical impactor with a 12.7 mm diameter and a total mass of 3.055kg. The impacted samples were square plates (100 × 100 mm) with a thickness of 15 mm and were tested on a circular support with a cut-out of 40 mm diameter.

2.2 Skin and sandwich structures characterization

Skin flexural performances were evaluated through 3- point bending tests. The experiments were carried out on samples with a 120 mm length, 20 mm width and 2 mm of thickness using a span length of 80 mm and a speed of 5 mm/min. The dynamic characterization by puncture tests for both skins and sandwich composites was carried out in the same conditions previously described for the core. The only differences are in sample thickness (2 mm for the skins and 19 mm for the panels) and in the impactor mass that was 8.055 kg in the case of sandwich panels.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Core Materials

The force-displacement curves obtained by shear tests are depicted in *Figure 2* whereas in *Table 1* are resumed the shear modulus and shear maximum strength values for each type of cork. It can be noticed how shear modulus and shear maximum strength tend to increase when cork density increases. Cork behavior progression at shear is shown in *Figure 3*. The same type of behavior was already studied and discussed by Reis and Silva [10]. It is worth noting that cork fracture in shear is of intergranular type and this means that samples failure has to be ascribed to binder collapse and not to cork damaging.

Samples	Shear Modulus (MPa)	Shear Maximum Strength (MPa)
NL10	1.00±0.05	0.26±0.04
NL20	1.26±0.04	0.57±0.03
NL25	1.92±0.27	0.75±0.04

Table 1: Cork shear modulus and shear maximum strength

Figure 2: Typical cork shear test curves

Figure 3: Cracks nucleation and propagation in a shear test on NL25

Bending tests results at room temperature are summarized in *Figure 4*. It appears clear that PVC foam shows higher flexural performances than cork displaying a higher modulus and a higher maximum strength. In *Figure 5* and *6* are represented the flexural performances of the different types of cork and of the PVC foam as a function of temperature. It is possible to notice that an increase in temperature leads to a progressive decrease in both flexural modulus and maximum strength. It is also necessary to consider that rising temperatures lead to a degradation of binder mechanical performances and so to a decrease in agglomerated cork performances. What has been said about flexural modulus is confirmed by DMA results (Dynamic mechanical analysis), that are not included in this study, where a decrease of storage modulus, E' , with temperature was detected. For PVC flexural modulus it has been noticed that it shows almost a constant value. A slight decrease of PVC flexural maximum strength can be observed when samples are tested at 80°C and even in this case these results are supported by

the ones obtained by DMA. In fact DMA highlighted that PVC foam has a glass transition temperature around 97°C and 108°C, which explains the progressive change in PVC behavior. PVC maximum strength trend is depicted in *Figure 6*.

Figure 4: Typical core flexural curves at room temperature

Figure 5: Cork (left) and PVC (right) flexural modulus as a function of temperature

Figure 6: Cork and PVC flexural maximum strength as a function of temperature

PVC foam shows better mechanical performances than cork also when it is subjected to compression tests. In *Figure 7* it is possible to notice that PVC foam displays a higher elastic modulus and a higher plateau load than all cork types, but it also exhibits a different compressive behavior. The synthetic foam is characterized by an initial elastic region that ends when the yielding point is reached. Cork compressive behavior is quite different because it follows the typical pattern of cellular materials and it was extensively studied by Anjos et al. [9][11], Rosa and Fortes [12], Pereira [4]. After an initial elastic region up to approximately 5 % deformation, which corresponds to cell walls elastic bending, it is possible to identify a wide plateau region that is due to the buckling of the cells. The third part of the curve is the densification region that appears earlier if cork density is higher. In this phase cell walls start touching each other and experiment mutual contact.

Figure 7: Typical core materials compression curves

Core materials strain rate sensitivity was investigated and PVC results are summarized in *Table 2*. In this case no strain rate sensitivity was detected as the average values of modulus and plateau load can be considered almost constant. The results obtained for cork show an opposite trend and are in agreement with the results obtained by Rosa and Fortes [12] who studied the strain rate sensitivity of cork planks in the three main directions. In particular an increase in compressive modulus and plateau load with speed for all cork families was found. This trend can be explained taking into account that the material struggles to adapt to the deformation when it is applied faster thus leading to a higher reaction force.

Test speed (mm/min)	Compressive Modulus (MPa)	Plateau load (MPa)
5	75.08±2.13	2.73±0.10
25	71.52±2.54	2.71±0.23
50	67.92±2.24	2.82±0.18
100	65.78±0.63	2.71±0.10
150	66.56±2.87	2.61±0.04
200	70.68±4.74	2.82±0.15

Table 2: PVC compressive modulus and plateau load depending on test speed

Temperature influence on compressive performances was investigated too. In *Figure 8* are represented the PVC compressive curves depending on the temperature. The increase in temperature leads to a decrease in PVC compressive modulus and plateau load and induces a clear change in PVC curves shape with the disappearance of peak strength. From cork point of view the compressive modulus and the plateau load trends are comparable with the trend of flexural performances. In *Figure 9* is possible to see the initiation and propagation of intergranular cracks depending on test temperature and, as a matter of fact, on binder degradation. The recovery results on cork have shown an increase in instantaneous recovery and in permanent deformation with tests speed for all cork types. It was also found out that the higher the cork density, the lower the instantaneous recovery and the higher the permanent deformation.

Figure 8: Typical PVC compression curves as a function of temperature

Figure 9: NL10 samples damaging at different temperature (first row). NL10 damage details at 80 °C (second row)

Dynamic compression tests have highlighted that NL10 and NL20 performances cannot be compared with HP130 ones. In particular these types of cork are only able to bear a 6J impact event. The situation is different in the case of NL25 that is able to bear a 13J impact event as HP130 does, undergoing a lower maximum deformation as depicted in *Figure 10*. The greatest difference in these two core materials is the energy absorbing mechanism. PVC absorbs energy only by permanent deformation whereas cork is able to absorb energy in a viscoelastic way recovering great part of its initial shape.

Figure 10: NL25 and HP130 maximum deformation after a 13J impact event

Puncture tests have highlighted that all types of cork have the same perforation threshold that is around 5J. HP130 is able to bear a higher impact energy reaching perforation around 10J. In *Figure 11* are summarized maximum displacement results. It is possible to notice that the higher the impact energy, the higher the displacement. It can be also seen that the cork with the lowest density is the one that undergoes always the maximum deformation while HP130 shows the lowest one. This behavior, coupled with the highest quasi-static mechanical properties, explain the greatest perforation threshold of PVC foam

Figure 11: Maximum displacement of all samples after puncture impact tests

3.2 Mechanical characterization of composite facesheets

Skins with (PPC) and without (PP) coupling agent were tested. In *Figure 12* three-point bending curves are depicted. It is clear the effect of coupling agent on composite laminate performances. The improvement of fiber-matrix interface allows to increase skin flexural modulus and flexural maximum strength.

The results obtained with puncture impact tests show an opposite trend in skin laminates performances. As it is possible to see in *Figure 13*, PP skins reach perforation after an impact event of 30J whereas PPC skins reach perforation already with a 20J impact event. These results can be explained considering that fibers have the capability to slip in the matrix without coupling agent thanks to the low interface adhesion thus allowing large deformation before fiber breakage. The results obtained agree with the ones obtained by Simeoli et al [13].

Figure 12: Typical three-point bending curves of composite skins

Figure 13: PP (left) and PPC (right) puncture impact test curves

3.3 Sandwich structures

Considering that HP130 core material shows higher mechanical performances than all type of corks and that a reasonable comparison can be made only with NL25, these two types of core materials were the only ones that were considered for the production of sandwich structures. In *Figure 14* are depicted the puncture test curves of NL25 core with PP and PPC skins. For both types of composite structures it is possible to notice an increase in maximum force and maximum displacement when impact energy increases. This can be explained considering that increasing impact energies lead to a higher deformation of the samples and so the reaction force that the sample exerts on the impactor is higher. In this graph it is also possible to identify the two typical peaks of force of sandwich structures that can be ascribed to the interaction of the impactor with the first and second skin. As already seen with the previous results on skins, PP sandwich structures show a higher resistance to impact than PPC

sandwich structure reaching perforation with an 80J impact event while PPC ones only with a 60J impact event.

Figure 14: Puncture impact curves for a PP (left) and PPC (right) sandwich structures made with a NL25 core

4 CONCLUSIONS

From the results obtained it appears clear that all types of cork show lower quasi-static mechanical performances than a traditional PVC synthetic foam, in fact they display a lower modulus and a lower maximum strength in all the tests performed. This can be ascribed to the fact that cork undergoes an intergranular fracture that depends mainly on cork granules and binder interface. This means that an increase in cork density can improve partially core performances, but the weakness of the material is always at the interface. Despite this cork displays great advantages from a dynamic point of view. Thanks to its cellular structure it can absorb high energy amounts with a limited extension of the damage along its thickness and with an exceptional recovery of the initial shape. Dynamic compression tests have highlighted how NL25 allows to bear the same impact energy of HP130 undergoing lower deformation and recovering its initial height to a greater extent. In the case of the skins coupling agent has an opposite effect in quasi-static and dynamic tests. In the first case it plays a major role in the improvement of fiber-matrix interface thus leading to an increase in composite mechanical performances. From a dynamic point of view the good interface does not allow fibers to slip in the matrix thus leading to fiber fracture for lower impact energy.

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